

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

THE PERCEPTION OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF A COLLEGE OF MEDICINE ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VIRTUAL TEACHING DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Background: The emergence of the SARS-CoV-2 infection in December 2019 led to significant disruption in traditional teaching and learning activities and the adoption of emergency remote teaching (ERT) and virtual platforms globally. This study aimed to determine the perception of students about the effectiveness, advantages, disadvantages, and challenges experienced with online teaching engagement during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology: A web-based survey of the classes via WhatsApp platforms was conducted among undergraduate students enrolled at the Lagos State University College of Medicine for the 2020–2021 academic session. The responses were exported and analysed using SPSS version 26.

Result: A total of four hundred and thirty-one (431) students participated, with an age range of 18–30 years and a mean of 22.1 ± 2.8 years. About two-thirds of the respondents were female, and the majority (66%) enrolled in medicine and surgery degrees. The mean score for the usefulness of online teaching was 4.12 ± 2.37 on a scale of 10. The most common perceived disadvantages of online teaching are being less interactive (46.3%) and boring (38.4%), while the most perceived advantages are the ease of studying at home (47.8%) and its flexibility (46.3%). The most common reasons for non-attendance at the online lecture are financial (204, 59.8%) (Lack of data), followed by poor internet connectivity (177, 57.9%). About 80% of the students experienced poor internet connectivity, 68% were distracted by activities in their homes, and 75% concluded that online teaching did not sufficiently enrich their academic knowledge. Headaches and eye aches were reported as health challenges following online teaching by 102 (30%) and 74 (21.7%), respectively.

Conclusion: This study revealed students' experiences with virtual learning and the barriers to its effectiveness in delivering the curriculum. The faculty and policymakers need to address the issues highlighted by the students to improve student experiences with such engagements.

Keywords: Online teaching, internet, perception, pandemic

Introduction

In December 2019, an unusual pneumonia was noted in Wuhan, China, which was initially linked to the wet market. The causative agent was later identified as the severe acute respiratory

syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS COV2), a beta coronavirus.¹

Infection from this virus assumed a pandemic proportion reported in more than 200 countries

with significant morbidity and mortality worldwide.

The pandemic caused significant disruption to routine as we knew it, with the closure of workplaces, schools, and countries operating at various levels of lockdown. With the premature closure of schools and lockdown lasting several months, teaching delivery mode shifted from regular face-to-face to online. The transmissibility of SARS-CoV-2 imposed restrictions on teacher-student interactions such that online teaching and learning activities were widely used despite the relaxation of lockdown in higher institutions. Online teaching mode is not new but not widely deployed in most institutions in Nigeria before the pandemic. At the peak of the lockdown, some universities embarked on online teaching for their numerous students. Some medical institutions were able to utilise this mode effectively in delivering their curriculum and conducting exit examinations for final-year medical students to join the workforce during the relaxation of the lockdown.

More than two years since the pandemic, higher institutions are entirely in session, and online teaching and learning activities are now more widely deployed. Since this mode of teaching-learning is relatively new to our system, it is a great idea to understand the perceptions of the students and their experience of virtual teaching. This feedback will be valuable in designing a sustainable online course delivery that will become integral to teaching and learning in higher institutions in Nigeria as it operates elsewhere.

This study aims to describe the students' perceptions at a college of medicine in Lagos about their teaching and learning experience during the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, it hopes to identify the barriers to effective online teaching and learning activities.

Methods

Recruitment

This cross-sectional study was conducted using a standardized online questionnaire designed using the Microsoft Office form based on previous studies on online teaching during the pandemic²⁻⁴. The questionnaire was sent to the students at the

Lagos State University College of Medicine Ikeja via the WhatsApp platform of each class.

Inclusion criteria: All the Students enrolled at the Lagos State University College of Medicine for the academic year 2020/21 in 200 level and above were eligible to participate.

Exclusion Criteria: Students who were enrolled but did not consent were excluded.

Sample size: Sample size was calculated based on the formula $nf = n/1 + (n/N)$

Where nf is the desirable sample size when the study population is less than 10,000

eligible student population = 693 = N

$n = z^2 PQ/d^2$

$n = 1.96^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 / 0.05^2 = 384$

z -standard estimate = 1.96

p = prevalence given as 0.5 in this study

$q = 1 - p$, d is precision = 0.05

where $n = 384$ is the estimate of the population

$nf = n/1 + (n/N)$

$nf = 384 / (1 + 384/693) = 384 / 1.554 = 247$

Adjusting for a response rate of 80% = $nf / 0.8$

Minimum sample size. = 309

The Survey instrument deployed is a questionnaire design from a similar study (11,13). The first section dealt with the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents.

The second section assessed participation in online classes, frequency, and reasons for non-attendance.

The third part considered the respondent's experience of an online class and its perceived usefulness. This was done by assessing how much the participant agreed with statements rated in a Likert manner. Ten Likert scale questionnaire was used to determine the overall perception among participants. Strongly disagree was the score as 0, disagree as 1, neutral as 2, agree as 3, and strongly agree as 4.

Students were asked to rate the overall usefulness from 0-10, where 0 denotes useless, and ten signifies extremely useful.

The fourth part assessed the perceived advantages, disadvantages, and common problems faced during online lectures.

This was circulated through the class WhatsApp groups for a period of two weeks in the month of April 2021.

Participation was voluntary and anonymous. Consent was taken at the beginning of the survey questionnaire.

Data analysis

Data collected was exported to Microsoft excel and analysed using SPSS version 25. Categorical variables were summarised as proportions and continuous variables in terms of means (with standard deviation). Chi-squared tests were used to assess the difference in proportions.

Results

Sociodemographic characteristics

Three hundred and forty-one (341) students participated in the study. The mean age of the participant was 22.1±2.8years with an age range of 18-30 years. Most of the students, 219 (64.2%), were females. Most of the students, 320(93.8%), attended at least one online teaching during the lockdown associated with the pandemic. Other sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in Table 1 Most participants were enrolled on the degree programme for Medicine and Surgery.

Figure 1. Overall Perception of virtual teaching

Perception of online teaching

The majority disagree with the statement that virtual teaching classes are better than face-to-face teaching, with 166(48.7%) strongly disagreeing and only 19(5.6%) strongly agreeing, and 54(15.8%) neutral. About 10% agreed / strongly agreed that teaching online is stimulating majority

12(32.8%) and 96(28.2), strongly disagree /disagree with this. Similarly, most of the respondents, 98(28.7) %, disagree / strongly disagree (105(30.8%) with the notion that they find it easy to engage in the lesson.

Most respondents were neutral to the statement, “I feel able to ask the question I want. More than half disagree/strongly disagree about enjoying online teaching. Well over 60% disagree/strongly disagree with the statement, ‘I prefer online teaching to face-to-face teaching.

Figure 2. Frequency of non-attendance at scheduled online classes during the pandemic

Association between overall perception and sociodemographic characteristics

The relationship between perception and sociodemographic characteristics of participants is shown in Table 3. There is a relationship between age and perception of online teaching. Older age groups are less likely to perceive virtual teaching negatively than younger participants. The gender of the participant did not influence their perception of online teaching. The undergraduate students in basic medical science (pharmacology and physiology have more negative perceptions than those in Medicine, Dentistry, and Nursing. Undergraduates with previous attendance at a virtual university teaching are more likely to have a positive perception.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 429)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age (in years)		
< 20	92	21.4
21 – 30	212	49.4
31 – 40	105	24.5
> 41	20	4.7
Level of Education		
None	12	2.8
Primary	77	17.9
Secondary	204	47.6
Tertiary	136	31.7
Employment Status		
Not working	86	20.0
Working for someone	73	17.0
Working for government	28	6.5
Self-employed	242	56.4
Marital Status		
Single	74	17.3
Married	301	70.2
Widowed	1	0.2
Divorced	4	0.9
Cohabiting	49	11.4
Place of Residence		
Semi-Urban	358	83.4
Rural	71	16.6

Table 2: Perceptions of participating Students to Online teaching and learning activities

	Agree N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Strongly Agree N (%)	Strongly Disagree N (%)
The teaching is stimulating	24(7)	96(28.2)	97(28.4)	12(3.5)	12(32.8)
I find it easy to engage with the lesson	35(10.3)	98(28.7)	85(24.9)	18(5.3)	105(30.8)
I feel able to ask the questions I want	90(26.4)	54(15.8)	108(31.7)	25(7.3)	64(18.8)
I enjoy the online teaching	31(9.1)	79(23.2)	91(26.7)	11(3.2)	129(37.8)
I would like the online teaching to be more interactive	94(27.6)	13(3.8)	131(38.4)	72(21.1)	31(9.1)
I feel the online teaching is as effective as face-to-face teaching	24(7)	103(30.2)	34(10)	12(3.5)	168(49.3)
I prefer online teaching to face to face	22(6.5)	81(23.8)	42(12.3)	30(8.8)	166(48.7)
The teachers are well prepared for teaching sessions	72(21.1)	48(14.1)	137(40.2)	26(7.6)	58(17)
My internet connections can be problematic	80(23.5)	6(1.8)	16(4.7)	233(68.3)	6(1.8)
Are virtual teaching better than face to face teaching mode?	18(5.3)	84(24.6)	54(15.8)	19(5.6)	166(48.7)

Figure 3. Perceived advantages of virtual teaching

Figure 4. Perceived disadvantages of Virtual teaching.

Non-attendance at scheduled online classes during the pandemic

The students responded to varying degrees of non-attendance at the scheduled online lecture. Only 25(7.3%) students attended all scheduled online teaching engagements.

Reason for non-attendance at scheduled online classes

The most frequent reason for non-attendance was financial (59.8%), while about half of the respondents had poor internet connectivity. Other reasons given are shown in Figure III.

Disadvantages of virtual teaching

The students perceived that virtual teaching provided ease of home study (47.8%), while a quarter of the respondent felt that flexibility was an advantage. An equal number did not find any benefit in virtual teaching. Less than one per cent thought that it gives a better understanding; the detail of this is shown in Figure 1V

About 46% (158) of the participants felt that virtual teaching is less interactive. About one-quarter of the respondents complained that it makes learning more expensive, more than a third of the students felt bored, while 21% opined that the students are easily distracted during virtual teaching. This is shown in Figure IV.

Perceived disadvantages

When asked about the usefulness of virtual teaching, 169(49.5%) opined that online instructions were not helpful, with 172(50.4%) agreed that it was worthwhile.

Further exploration of peculiar individual problems experienced with online teaching showed that poor internet connectivity was the most frequently encountered problem experienced by almost 80% of students. About three-quarters felt the lectures needed to enrich their academic knowledge sufficiently. 232 (68%) participants reported distraction by activities at home; other problems noted were the inadequate explanation of concepts (42.2%), multiple cancellations (33.7%), 128(37.5%) felt the lecturer were too fast, time clashes, and need for rescheduling was reported by 56(16.4%). This is shown in Figure V:

Poor internet connectivity was the topmost challenge for virtual teaching experienced by almost 80% of the participant. About three-

quarters of the participants felt their knowledge was not sufficiently enriched, while distraction from activities at home was a problem for 232(68%) of the respondents. 96(28.2) experienced some health complaints following virtual teaching.

Discussion

The SARSCOV-2 infection emergence and its transmissibility, morbidity, and mortality led to a massive change in social norms. This includes lockdowns, social distancing, closure of schools, and the need to continue education outside the school environment. More than 24 months into Nigeria's pandemic, most educational institutions have resumed but with changes to the mode of engaging students in learning.

In Nigeria, the COVID-19 pandemic provided an opportunity for utilizing digital learning, which was previously under-utilized. This engagement is not without limitations despite the alternative educational system it offered during the pandemic that culminated in the resumption of teaching, thus eliminating the risk of losing an academic session.

In a recent cross-sectional study including several medical schools in 12 different countries (Bulgaria, Canada, Greece, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Spain, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Turkey, Ukraine, USA) involving over 3,000 medical students¹², Stoebr et al. showed that more than 78% of the schools rapidly switched to online learning.

Although our study did not target the schools, unlike our analysis, most students were satisfied with the quantity (67%) and quality (62%) of their online engagement.

This is much higher than our study, and the reason may include prior utilization of online teaching, better infrastructure to support, and familiarity of students with various platforms. In Nigeria, the online mode has not been previously popular, and utilizing this during the pandemic was associated with some difficulties.

In another study to examine the impact of COVID-19 on 674 Japanese medical students, Sekine et al. concluded that face-to-face classes were preferable to an electronic learning environment¹⁵.

In Uganda, Olum et al. assessed medical education and e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic:

by evaluating awareness, attitudes, preferences, and barriers among undergraduate medicine and nursing students at Makerere University¹⁶. This study was similarly designed to ours, web-based research involving 221 participants, with most of them in the MBBS programme. About half of the participants believed that e-learning reduces the quality of knowledge attained and is not an efficient teaching method. Monthly income, internet connectivity quality, computer ownership and frequency of usage of academic websites or applications significantly affected attitudes towards e-learning. Similar to our findings, internet costs, poor internet connectivity, and family distractions were the most critical barriers to e-learning.¹⁷

Noha et al. in Egypt conducted a cross-sectional study amongst 340 students via an online survey similar to our methodology. The mean age of the respondent was 19.57 ± 1.02 , ranging from 17 to 23 years; 61% were females.¹⁷ About 63.8% of students had no previous experience with online learning. In that study, like ours, perceived advantages of online teaching were the ability to stay home to learn, comfortable surroundings and access to online materials. The main perceived disadvantages were technical problems, lack of patient interaction, and reduced teacher interaction.

Most students found face-to-face learning superior to online learning in improving their knowledge¹³⁻¹⁶. However, our study, like that conducted in the UK, showed that the students would like online teaching to be more interactive¹⁸. This could be achieved via students' response systems that can be incorporated into the teaching, for example, polls, quizzes or break-out rooms, all of which are available on most online platforms. However, faculty inexperience and inadequate training in utilising digital media for teaching were limitations that were inherent at the onset.

Endo et al., in a review of the cross-country learning in Africa during the COVID-19 pandemic, explored the challenges and innovations brought by the pandemic in medical and pharmacy education and noted that both staff and students in Africa face multiple challenges and will require various measures to address.¹⁹

Finally, online teaching and learning activities became a panacea for continuing medical education during the COVID-19 pandemic. The

lockdown, social distancing, and school closures ensued, making alternative teaching methods necessary. However, the acute nature did not provide any opportunity to ramp up facilities to cope with this new method. This, coupled with poor internet facilities, digital illiteracy, and financial implications, all added to challenges for educators and learners.

This study highlights the students' perceptions of the effectiveness of online teaching. Generally, students felt it could have been more effective t face-to-face mode. This information is vital in building a formidable digital platform that can effectively deliver qualitative and qualitative education. It will also make it easier to address the highlighted barriers, such as poor internet access and the cost of digital learning.

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Declarations

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Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

None

Code availability

Not available

Authors' Contributions

OO A conceived the project, OOA, OT O, YA K, OOO drafted the questionnaire, Collected the data OOA, OT O, YAK, OOO, analysed and wrote the manuscripts

Ethics approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (HREC-LASUTH). LREC/06/10/1525

Consent to participate

Obtained from participants

Consent for publication

Obtained from participants.

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